

LIBRA: Light based multi-sensing device for screening of pathogens and nutrients in bioreactors

Main Objectives

Project LIBRA aims to develop a benchtop multi-sensing system for automated screening of analytes and biomolecules in diverse bioreactors. Differentiated by advanced integration technologies, LIBRA is meant to enable state-of-the-art integrated photonic devices. These modules are designed to analyze bioreactor samples, providing detailed insights into nutrient compositions and pathogen presence. The device will be able to be adjusted to various bioreactor systems from stirred tank to single use bioreactors (SUB). This project pioneers a new era in bioreactor sample analysis where precision, efficiency, and innovation converge.

Applications

LIBRA's initiative centers around developing a dynamic, compact, efficient, and cost-effective Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC). This chip integrates laser sources for Raman and aMZI platforms, along with individual detectors for each module. It will leverage two cutting-edge light-based sensing modules: a Raman spectrometer and an aMZI refractive index sensing module, both utilizing our TriPlex[®] silicon nitride platform. The outcome is a sophisticated, all-encompassing solution that promises to elevate the capabilities of bioreactor sample analysis.

In the Raman sensing module, we enhance sensitivity by integrating accurate, fast tunable 780 and 850 nm light sources, utilizing stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) and Waveguide Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (WERS) techniques. Novel waveguides with integrated spectrometers, including Arrayed Waveguide Grating (AWG) and digital Fourier Transform (dFT) designs, improve Raman scattering collection efficiency. The aMZI sensing platform, sensitive to material changes, employs a sensing window for high-accuracy characterization in diagnostic applications. Both Raman and aMZI sensor chips will be combined in a single cartridge, utilizing a unique integration process with disposable microfluidic modules for modular, interchangeable components, facilitating bioreactor sample screening.

The LIBRA platform introduces a system poised to revolutionize overall cultivation processes, contributing to great advancements. This innovation is set to establish industrial leadership across diverse applications, including but not limited to biofuels, environmental protection (e.g., microalgae for wastewater treatment), and the energy market (microalgae hydrogen production).

Figure 1. Impression of the final module integration in dedicated cartridges.

Figure 2. Concept of the active and passive chips

LIBRA fact sheet

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Project website:

www.libraproject.eu

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Consortium:

- National Technical University of Athens (GR)
- LioniX International B.V. (NL)
- CSEM – Centre Suisse D’électronique et de microtechnique SA – Recherche et développement (CH)
- Optagon Photonics (GR)
- Fibo Labs Oy (FI)
- DEMCON Advanced Mechatronics Enschede B.V (NL)
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- SCINUS cell expansion Netherlands B.V. (NL)
- AARHUS Universitet (DK)
- ECOVAMED (FR)

The Role of LioniX International

LioniX International will design and manufacture the photonic chips, based on our proprietary silicon nitride technology, TriPleX®. Our involvement spans the entire device development process, from functional design to wafer-level hybrid integration. This design includes the circuit layouts essential for biosensing devices, employing various optimized TriPleX® waveguide types tailored for specific applications.

The circuit design encompasses the creation of dedicated circuitries and etched pockets for hybrid integration of other platforms.

Another contribution will be the development of a wafer-level hybrid integration scheme, involving new cleanroom processes and microstructures for testing integrated components. The sensing windows on the chips will be customized for LIBRA. The lasers used in this application will have central wavelengths at 780 nm and 850 nm. Both will feature 50 nm tunability around the central wavelengths to make the Raman sensing window large enough to probe the different samples that may pass through the microfluidic cartridges.

We will also advise on electronic components for testing the Raman balance detector and aMZI sensing module.

Roadmap

- Development of miniaturized Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) on the TriPleX® platform, serving as modules for Raman spectroscopy, and refractive index sensing.
- Design of both active and passive sensing chips, with a focus on determining the ideal waveguide cross-section for optimized operation.
- Fabrication of active and passive TriPleX® chips in two distinct rounds. The initial round involves an active run with flip-chip integration features, encompassing metal contacts and more. Subsequently, a passive run will fabricate dedicated wafers featuring sensing windows for aMZI sensors and a waveguide-based spiral for the Raman sensing module.
- Characterization of the fabricated TriPleX® PICs outlined in the previous objective. This encompasses all fabricated building blocks, starting from tunable lasers, spectrometers, and passive sensing chips. A multi-channel fiber array will be employed for characterization, connecting light sources and detectors.

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Our chips drive your business

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